

Effects of *Cannabis sativa* on Neuromuscular and Cognitive Functions of Albino Wistar Rat. (*Rattus norvegicus*)

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ABSTRACT

Cannabis Sativa, commonly known as marijuana is a recreational drug that has a potential for abuse especially among the youths over the years and in several countries hence it is widely considered an illicit drug. Despite these, there are some beneficial needs of this drug which we need to find out especially on the neuromuscular and cognitive system of the body. Therefore the, present study is out to investigate the effect of cannabis sativa on the neuromuscular and cognitive behavior of albino rats. Twenty four young rats (24) were used for the study. They were divided into six groups of four animals per group. Group 1 served as the control while groups 2-6 were daily administered 10mg/kg, 20mg/kg, 40mg/kg, 80mg/kg, and 160mg/kg of *Cannabis sativa*, respectively for 28 days. After 20 days of administration. The rats were subjected to several behavioral tests, including the handgrip test, beam walking test, inverted screen test, navigational maze test, Morris water maze, and forced swim test, to assess their muscle strength, coordination, and cognitive function. The rats' weight was also monitored throughout the study period. The results showed that *Cannabis sativa* had a significant impact on the neuromuscular and cognitive behavior of the rats. It significantly increased muscle strength in handgrip, and significantly reduced coordination in beam walking. Inverted screen test, navigational maze test and Morris water maze test did not have any significant difference, forced swimming test demonstrated high alertness and anti-depression tendency. The weight of rats also increase in the treatment groups than the control during the period These findings suggest that *Cannabis sativa* has a positive impact on the neuromuscular strength and also serve as an antidepressant. If this is well extrapolated to human, it can have some physiological benefits in our society when taken in a moderate and recommended dose.

Keywords: *Cannabis sativa*, memory, neuromuscular function.

INTRODUCTION

Cannabis Sativa, commonly known as marijuana, is a widely recognized and utilized plant species in many parts of the world. Despite its widespread popularity, it is considered an illicit drug in the majority of countries globally [1]. Its other names include Indian hemp, weed, Igbo, pot, and other names generic to the particular area that is used. The popularity of *Cannabis sativa* as a recreational drug cannot be overstated, an estimated 2.5% of the world's population, or 147 million

individuals, use cannabis annually [2].

The use of *Cannabis sativa* is not limited to any specific age group, as both young and older people partake in its use. The most common method of use is through smoking, but other ways of consumption include oral ingestion in food and drinks or vaping [3]. The use of marijuana is often motivated by its ability to release dopamine, providing a feeling of euphoria and pleasure, making it a popular performance enhancer for various activities such as studying,

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sex, and more, among young people [4]. In some tribes in Nigeria, marijuana is mixed with other substances and used for medicinal, religious, and recreational purposes. For instance, the Ijaw tribe of southern Nigeria mixes hemp with locally brewed alcohol, and this mixture is referred to as "Monkey tail" and is served to men on special occasions [5].

Despite the negative perception surrounding the use of *Cannabis sativa* due to its potential for abuse, and the effects it causes such as cognitive impairment, euphoria, and addiction, there are several beneficial uses of *Cannabis* that have been documented. For example, *Cannabis* has been shown to relieve neuropathic pain [6] and to be an effective sleep inducer for people experiencing insomnia [2]. The versatility of the *Cannabis* plant is reflected in its various forms, from oil extracts from the seeds and leaves to powdered forms, ointments, and more. Additionally, the roots and stem of the plant have been shown to have great potential in various areas of research [7].

Apart from the traditional use of *Cannabis*, it has great potential in the pharmaceutical industry and has been used in the production of drugs and cosmetics. Despite the numerous benefits of *Cannabis sativa*, its full potential is yet to be fully explored and utilized, while the dangers of abuse and addiction associated with the use of *Cannabis* have dominated the narrative surrounding its use, it is important to recognize and acknowledge the numerous beneficial uses and applications of this versatile plant species.

The abuse of *Cannabis sativa* is becoming increasingly prevalent across the world especially among the youths. However, despite its growing use, the effects of *Cannabis Sativa* on the human body remain a subject of much debate and speculation. While some studies have shown that *Cannabis sativa* can have therapeutic benefits for individuals suffering from neuropathic pain, there is a lack of comprehensive

research on its effects on the neuromuscular and cognitive systems [8]. This is a critical issue, as these systems play a crucial role in maintaining overall health and well-being of an individual. The purpose of this study is to address this gap in the literature and shed light on the impact of *Cannabis sativa* on the neuromuscular and cognitive behaviors of individuals. This finding in this study will contribute to a better understanding of the potential effects of *Cannabis sativa* on the human body [9]. Ultimately, this research aims to enhance our knowledge and help to ensure the safe use of *Cannabis sativa*. One of the challenges in studying the effects of *Cannabis sativa* is its addictive properties, which is a common trait among recreational drugs [10]; [11]. *Cannabis* is considered to be less addictive compared to other substances, but it has still been linked to increased vulnerability to addiction and other disorders [10]; [11]. To better understand the effects of *Cannabis sativa*, researchers have focused on the plant's bioactive compounds, which are usually in the form of oil and aqueous solutions [1]. The bioactive compounds of *Cannabis sativa* include two main components:

Δ^9 -tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) and cannabidiol (CBD) [12]. THC is the psychoactive component of the plant, meaning it is responsible for the "high" commonly associated with its use [13]. On the other hand, CBD is not psychoactive and has been shown to have a number of potential therapeutic benefits, such as reducing anxiety and inflammation [14]; [15].

Despite the potential benefits of *Cannabis sativa*, there are also a number of negative consequences associated with its use. For example, THC has been linked to cognitive impairments, such as decreased learning and memory, as well as negatively impacting coordination [16]; [17]. Additionally, the use of *Cannabis sativa* has also been linked to an increased risk of addiction and other disorders [12]; [18].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was done in the Department of Animal and Environmental Biology animal house University Campus, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria

Cannabis sativa was collected locally from a farmer in Ogbia local government area of Bayelsa State, after accessing a permit.

The twenty-four (24) albino rats weighing between 75g and 100g.were purchased from the Department of

Preparation of *Cannabis sativa* with ethanol.

One hundred and eighty grammes (180g) of *Cannabis sativa* of the seeds and leaves was blended and soaked into 4L of alcohol and was left for 48 hours Thereafter, it was filtered with Whatman filter paper (number one)

Experimental Design

A total of 8.5g alcohol extract was, to produce the different concentrations of the extracts for the different groups (10mg/kg, 20mg/kg, 40mg/kg, 80mg/kg, and 160mg/kg for groups 2,3,4,5 and 6.) according to their different weights. The

Handgrip Test

The handgrip test is an experimental test used to determine the muscle strength of the animal. During the test, experimental rats were made to hang using their forelimbs and suspend in the air on a line that was linked to two poles and then a

Beam Walking

The Beam walking test checks the animal's motor coordination and balancing. A wooded rod was placed across two poles and food was placed at both ends of the rod, the rat was placed in the middle to walk to either end of the rod and given a time frame of 240 seconds to get to the food. The

Inverted Screen Test

During this test, the rats were placed under wire gauge to hold the wire with its four limbs and the stopwatch was started simultaneously. How long it took it

Navigational Maze

The navigational Maze is a test used to evaluate the learning and memory capacity of animals; it is also important in determining the cognition of animals and their ability

human Physiology animal house, University of Port Harcourt. They were grouped into six (6) groups according to their weights in sequence. The animals were acclimatized for fourteen (14) days during which they were maintained under the standard condition of twelve hours' light/dark cycles at room temperature and fed with grower's mash feed and water. Their weights were taken every week.

the filtrate was concentrated by the use of the rotary evaporator it was then placed in a water bath system and evaporated to dryness of which 8.5 g of the extract was formed

extracts were administered orally, and daily for twenty-eight days. The rats from each group were subjected to different tests after 20 days of administration and the results were recorded.

stopwatch was simultaneously switched on to record how long the rats hold unto the line before it falls (Deacon, 2013). The test was performed five consecutive times for each rat, among the six groups.

rat was monitored to see if it will be coordinated to move to the food within 240 seconds and if not, it was removed and another rat placed. This test was conducted five consecutive times with every animal in each group.

to hold unto the inverted screen was measured. A soft landing platform was place under the rats to safe them from injury as they fall off.

to explore and navigate. The rat was placed in a navigational maze and a stopwatch immediately started. The rats were given 300 seconds to complete the exercise. Any rat that

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did not complete within that period was removed;. This test was done five times for each rat in the six groups

Morris Water Maze

The Morris Water Maze test is a behavioral test used in the study of learning and memory, this test is based on the fact that an animal will try to escape a stressful situation or stimulus. In this case, it will be a pool of water and a platform was placed where it is visible. The rats were

trained to know where the platform was located and then placed inside the water to navigate and find the platform. This test was carried out five times for each rat across the six groups.

Forced Swim Test

The forced swim test is a behavioral test used to determine the depression effect of a drug on animals, it was used mostly in evaluating the effect of an anti-depressant drug, and experimental manipulations that are aimed at rendering or preventing depression-like states. The rat was

placed in a large tank containing water and where the limbs of the rat will not reach the bottom when the rat is placed in the tank. The rat was observed and timed how long it takes to swim before getting tired. This test was conducted five times for each rat across the six groups.

Weight

The weight of each rat across each group was recorded every week and the weights were taken note of during the study. The standard deviation and standard error of the mean (SEM) were calculated for each group using

the SPSS version 16 where the Analyses of variance (ANOVA) was carried out and the result was deemed significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$.

RESULTS

Result from the Test

Handgrip

The results of the handgrip test indicated that Group 2 which received doses of 10mg/kg, performed best with mean values of (123.4 ± 13.08) The control group, Group 1, had the lowest muscular

strength performance. A significant difference in muscular strength performance was observed between the groups where administration took place and the control group, (Table 1 , fig 1)

Figure 1: Results of the rat's performance during the handgrip Test across the groups.

Table 1: Result of the Handgrip Test across Five Trials of the Six Groups

GROUPS	TRIAL 1	TRIAL 2	TRAIL 3	TRAIL 4	TRAIL 5	MEAN
GRP1	24.5±5.18	21.75±5.44	25.25±4.46	35±10.40	24.75±3.98	26.25±4.99
GRP2	233±86.91	141.75±31.72	90.25±26.69	89±23.17	63±14.90	123.4±24.02 ^c
GRP3	71.25±43.39	43.5±19.20	32±10.41	25.5±9.86	38.25±6.68	42.4±13.08 ^a
GRP4	106±28.61	58±12.57	46.5±13.04	23.5±4.90	49.25±6.65	56.65±8.75 ^{ab}
GRP5	95.5±23.64	64±10.08	61.75±9.80	35.5±	34.5±6.65	58.25±8.99 ^{ab}
GRP6	106.5±21.70	89.5±20.91	87.25±7.73	35±5.77	42.25±7.70	72.1±8.45 ^b

Values are presented in mean ± SEM (n=4) $p \leq 0.05$, mean values having the same alphabetical superscripts are not statistically different.

Beam Walking

The mean and standard deviation of the data collected from the beam walking test were analyzed. The coordination of the rats was evaluated by providing them with a 240-second time frame to walk across the beam. The results indicated that Group 2, which received a 10mg/kg dose, displayed the longest walking time across the beam and the lowest coordination with a mean value of (137.55 ± 35.95). On the other hand, Group 1 the control group displayed the shortest walking time across the beam with a mean value of (51.05 ± 16.25). The control group displayed the highest level of performance in walking across the beam compared to all the administered groups, and a significant difference was observed between the control group and the administered groups (fig.2, Table2)

Figure 2: the performance of rats in the Beam walking test across the groups

Table 2: Result of the Beam walking Test Across Five Trials of The Six Group

GROUPS	TRIAL 1	TRIAL 2	TRIAL 3	TRIAL 4	TRIAL 5	MEAN
GRP1	80.5±50.06	38.5±14.08	63±28.55	48.75±24.80	24.5±10.87	51.05±16.25
GRP2	104.75±45.67	148±50.67	185.5±46.84	124.5±66.70	125±66.39	137.55±35.95a
GRP3	141.25±57.48	71.25±56.46	67.75±57.50	63.5±58.83	70.5±56.75	82.85±53.40
GRP4	134.5±43.34	116.5±54.65	40.5±2651.	83.5±54.56	102±55.20	95.4±26.70a
GRP5	107.25±47.54	131.25±62.80	161.25±55.39	136.75±59.65.	129.75±63.85	133.25±13.35a
GRP6	127.5±58.22	104.5±51.46	132±62.88	87±53.22	97±56.86	109.6±6.67a

Values are presented in mean ± SEM (n=4) $p \leq 0.05$, mean values having the same alphabetical superscripts are not statistically different

Inverted Screen Test

The results showed that Group 1 (the control group) had the best performance, with a mean value of (98.2 ± 17.35). In contrast, Group 3 had the lowest performance with a mean value of (44 ± 22.36) and a dose of 40mg/kg. Both Group 2 and Group

4 demonstrated high performance with mean values of (91.1 ± 91.1) and (97.8 ± 15.35), respectively. There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in performance between Group 1 (the control group) Group 2 and Group 4, (Fig. 3, Table 3).

Figure 3: The result of the inverted Screen Test across the Groups

Table 3: Result of The Inverted screen test Across Five Trials of The Six Groups

GROUPS	TRIAL 1	TRIAL 2	TRIAL 3	TRIAL 4	TRIAL 5	MEAN
GRP1	115±48.02	113.5±19.66	136.25±33.90	54±3.31	72.25±11.09	98.2±17.35
GRP2	87.5±7.41	112.25±13.10	81±10.50	81±7.85	93.75±10.85	91.1±91.1
GRP3	36±7.22	48.75±25.04	75.25±50.19	33.25±16.74	26.75±14.61	44±22.36a
GRP4	181.5±41.87	113.25±17.57	81.75±12.07	57.5±4.97	55±4.60	97.8±15.35
GRP5	101.5±41.87	67.25±15.17	47±10.10	34.5±4.97	40±6.68	58.05±11.61a
GRP6	109.75±29.05	76.5±24.37	72±15.95	48±5.30	48.25±8.28	70.9±11.90a

Values are presented in mean ± SEM (n=4) p ≤ 0.05, mean values having the same alphabetical superscripts are not statistically different

Navigational Maze Test

The results showed that Group 2, which received a 10mg/kg dose, had the longest navigation period with a mean of (231.1 ± 28.97), while Group 6, which received a 160mg/kg dose, had the best performance in

navigating the test, with a mean of (138.35 ± 19.01). When compared to the control group, there were no significant difference between the control and the treatment groups (Fig.4 Table 4)

Figure 4: the performance of the rats during the Navigational test

Table 4: Result of the Navigational maze test Across Five Trials of The Six Groups

GROUPS	TRIAL 1	TRIAL 2	TRIAL 3	TRIAL 4	TRIAL 5	MEAN
GRP1	153±64.92	176.75±43.28	148.75±55.75	174.25±56.97	256.25±43.75	181.8±30.08
GRP2	133.75±55.50	203.25±56.89	221.75±53.56	300±0.00	296.75±3.25	231.1±28.97
GRP3	157.5±71.19	242.5±57.5	234.25±65.75	148±56.58	194±60.20	195.25±51.89
GRP4	190±44.37	184±67/42	274.25±25.75	162.5±79.41	240±60.00	210.15±38.96
GRP5	172.75±45.26	126.25±60.20	178±50.95	250.25±49.75	163±79.11	178.05±25.78
GRP6	116.75±61.29	92±14.39	62.5±22.73	170.75±75.86	249.75±46.65	138.35±19.01

Values are presented in mean ± SEM (n=4) p ≤ 0.05, mean values having the same alphabetical superscripts are not statistically different

Morris Water Maze

The results showed that Group 3, with a dose of 20mg/kg and a mean of (4.9 ± 2.37), demonstrated the fastest performance and was able to learn and find the platform quickest. On the other hand, Group 5, with a

dose of 80mg/kg and a mean of (10.95 ± 3.05), had the lowest performance. The result was not so significantly different from the control (Fig.5, Table 5)

Figure .5: the performance in the Morris Water maze Test across the groups

Table 5: Result of The Morris Water Test Across Five Trials of The Six Groups

GROUPS	TRIAL 1	TRIAL 2	TRIAL 3	TRIAL 4	TRIAL 5	MEAN
GRP1	13±11.00	5.75±2.86	14.5±11.84	4.32±1.7	2.5±0.86	7.7±5.51
GRP2	14±12.00	5.5±2.39	5.75±3.75	4.75±2.05	2.25±0.47	6.45±3.99
GRP3	15±5.89	12.33±5.48	2.67±0.57	1.67±0.28	0.75±0.00	4.9±2.37a
GRP4	15.5±6.70	3.5±1.14	2.75±0.75	2.5±0.64	2±0.40	5.25±1.05a
GRP5	41.25±12.02	7±2.12	1.18±1.18	1.75±0.47	2±1.0	10.95±3.05a
GRP6	17.5±5.23	6±2.04	3±0.57	2.75±0.47	1.75±0.47	6.2±1.06a

Values are presented in mean ± SEM (n=4) p ≤ 0.05, mean values having the same alphabetical superscripts are not statistically different

Forced Swim Test

The results revealed that Group 5, which received a dose of 80mg/kg, displayed the highest level of mobility with a mean duration of (267.4 ± 8.65a). On the other hand, Group 1, the control group, displayed

the lowest level of mobility with a mean duration of (26.65 ± 4.12). It was concluded that all groups that received administration showed improved mobility compared to the control group (Fig 6 Table 6),

Figure 6: the performance during the forced Swim test across the groups
Table 6: Result of The Swimming Test Across Five Trials of The Six Groups

Values are presented in mean \pm SEM (n=4) $p \leq 0.05$, mean values having the same

GROUPS	TR1	TR2	TR3	TR4	TR5	MEAN
GRP1	6.5 \pm 10.31	32.5 \pm 3.79	15 \pm 2.08	9.5 \pm 1.93	11.25 \pm 3.19	26.65 \pm 4.12
GRP2	161 \pm 29.62	133 \pm 18.35	107.25 \pm 6.60	76 \pm 11.36	48.25 \pm 7.72	105.1 \pm 8.95 ^a
GRP3	109 \pm 11.81	64.75 \pm 9.17	70.25 \pm 3.30	45.5 \pm 5.68	37.5 \pm 3.86	65.4 \pm 22.43 ^a
GRP4	183.5 \pm 19.44	144.25 \pm 32.03	144.5 \pm 41.40	131.25 \pm 30.88	80.5 \pm 7.98	136.8 \pm 19.29 ^a
GRP5	401.25 \pm 69.19	361.25 \pm 33.44	282.25 \pm 15.94	147.5 \pm 23.70	144.75 \pm 40.15	267.4 \pm 8.65 ^a
GRP6	241 \pm 16.23	120.75 \pm 39.18	85.5 \pm 21.61	50.5 \pm 11.02	42.5 \pm 7.50	108.05 \pm 17.72 ^a

alphabetical superscripts are not statistically different

Weight

The results revealed that there was an increase in weight among the groups

that received the treatment compared to the control group(fig 7)

Figure 7: change in weights of the rats in each group during the study period.

DISCUSSION

The present study is aimed to investigate the effects of Cannabis sativa on the neuromuscular and cognitive functions of rats. to achieve this, different tests were used to ascertain its effects, The handgrip test, and inverted screen tests were used to ascertain the muscular strength, but inverted screen test

also ascertain coordination and with beam walking test, the coordination of the rats was studied. The navigational maze test and Morris water maze test deal with the ability of the rats to learn and their memory while the forced swimming test was performed to assess the anxiety levels. Coordination, learning, and

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memory were parts of the cognition system.

The handgrip test results showed that all rats administered with *Cannabis sativa* exhibited improved muscle strength compared to the control group. This suggests that the consumption of *Cannabis sativa* may have a positive impact on the neuromuscular system. The results of the inverted screen test showed no significant difference between the control group and the administered groups except groups 2 and 4 with doses of 10mg/kg and 40mg/kg respectively. In contrast, the beam walking test showed that the control group had better coordination compared to the groups administered with *Cannabis sativa*. This suggests that the consumption of *Cannabis sativa* may have a negative impact on coordination. This agrees with the findings of [17] who reported that *Cannabis* influences musculoskeletal coordination.

The navigational maze test showed that Group 6 with a dose of 160mg/kg had the best navigational abilities, even compared to all the groups. These results suggest that *Cannabis sativa* may have positive effects on learning and memory. The Morris water maze test showed that Group 3 with a dose of 20mg/kg, had a better performance than all other groups, including the control group though the difference was not statistically significant due to the wide standard error of mean. These results provide further evidence for the potential positive effects of *Cannabis sativa* on learning and memory this agrees with the work of [19] who opined that *Cannabis* increase cognitive functions. It also agrees with the work of [20] who reveals several therapeutic values of *Cannabis*. The

forced swim test showed that all rats administered with *Cannabis sativa* exhibited a higher level of anxiety compared to the control group. This suggests that the consumption of *Cannabis sativa* may have a negative impact on anxiety levels in rats. This agrees with the findings of [21] who agreed that forced swimming test is good for antidepressant test.

For learning and memory, *Cannabis* has been known to heighten sensitivity, and the result of the navigational maze and the Morris Water tests showed that it helps for learning. This is consistent with previous research, which has shown that *Cannabis sativa* has the potential to improve memory function, particularly in the context of aging or neurological disorders. It was observed that the treated group have an increased weight than the control. This could be because it increases appetite hence increasing the quantity of food consumed. This agrees with the work of [22] who suggested that *Cannabis* supplement can increase broilers performance.

The research aimed to understand the effects of *cannabis* on the muscle strength, coordination, learning, and memory of albino rats, using tests like handgrip, beam walking and more, from the result, there is a better understanding of *Cannabis sativa* like how it can increase the muscle strength, and it causes coordination impairment at certain doses, it can improve or heighten the learning and memory.

I suggest that the use of *cannabis* as a medicinal substance be allowed, however, with appropriate regulation to allow for further research to gain a deeper understanding of its effects on various biological systems.

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